

ON FUZZY SUPRA ALMOST P-SPACES

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Abstract.

The concept of Almost P-spaces in classical topology was introduced by A.I.Veksler [16] as P'-spaces and was also studied further by R.Levy [7] and C.I. Kim [6]. The aim of this paper is to introduce and study the notion of fuzzy supra almost P-spaces and various characterizations of fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are established.

Keywords:

Fuzzy supra F_σ -set, Fuzzy supra G_δ -set, Fuzzy supra nowhere dense set, Fuzzy supra dense set, Fuzzy supra P-Space, Fuzzy supra almost P-Space.

1. Introduction

In the year 1965, L. A.Zadeh [17] was first introduced the concept of fuzzy sets and fuzzy set operations in his classical paper. In 1968, the theory of fuzzy topological spaces was introduced and developed by C.L.Chang [4]. In 1983, Mashhour.A.S.et.al.,[8] introduced and studied the concept of Supra topological spaces. In 1987, Abd El-monsef et.at [1] introduced the concepts of fuzzy supra topological as a natural generalization of the notion of supra topological spaces. In 1972, Mishra.A.K [9] introduced the concepts of P-spaces as a generalization of ω_α -additive spaces of Sikorski [13] and Cohen.L.W and Goffman.C [5]. The concept of P-spaces in fuzzy setting was introduced by Thangaraj.G and Balasubramanian.G [15]. The concept of fuzzy supra P-spaces and weak fuzzy supra P-spaces was introduced and studied by the author in [11,12].

In this paper, fuzzy supra almost P-spaces is introduced and studied. It is established that fuzzy supra G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra residual sets in fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets. It is obtained that fuzzy supra σ -boundary sets in fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are either fuzzy supra first category sets which are not dense or fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 [1].

A collection S^* of fuzzy sets in a set M is called fuzzy supra topology on M if the following conditions are satisfied:

- 1) $\mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}$ belongs to S^* .
- 2) $g_\chi \in S^*$ for each $\chi \in \Lambda$ implies $(\bigvee_{\chi \in \Lambda} g_\chi) \in S^*$.

The pair (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra topological space. The elements of S^* are called

fuzzy supra open sets and the complement of a fuzzy supra open set is called fuzzy supra closed set.

Definition: 2.2 [10]

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra topological space and B be a fuzzy set in M , then the fuzzy supra closure and fuzzy supra interior of B defined respectively as

$$cl^*(B) = \bigwedge \{ g / g \text{ is a fuzzy supra closed set in } U \text{ and } B \leq g \}$$

$$int^*(B) = \bigvee \{ g / g \text{ is a fuzzy supra open set in } U \text{ and } g \leq B \}$$

Definition: 2.3 [10]

Let (U, T) be a fuzzy topological space and S^* be a fuzzy supra topology on U . We call S^* a fuzzy supra topology associated with T if $T \leq S^*$.

Remark: 2.4 [1]

- (1). Every fuzzy topological space is a fuzzy supra topological space.
- (2). If (M, S^*) is an associated fuzzy supra topological space with the fuzzy topological space (M, S) , then every fuzzy open(closed) set in the fuzzy topological space (M, S) is fuzzy supra open(closed) set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) .

Lemma 2.5 [4]

For a fuzzy set B in a fuzzy topological space M ,

- (i) $1 - int^*(B) = cl^*(1 - B)$,
- (ii) $1 - cl^*(B) = int^*(1 - B)$.

Definition 2.6 [3]

A fuzzy supra open set B in fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) if $B = \bigvee_{i=1}^\infty (B_i)$, where $1 - B_i \in S^*$ for $i \in I$,

Definition 2.7 [3]

A fuzzy supra open set B in fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) if $B = \bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty (B_i)$, where $B_i \in S^*$ for $i \in I$.

Definition 2.8 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra dense set if there exists no fuzzy supra closed set D in (M, S^*) such that $B < D < 1$. That is, $cl^*(B) = 1$, in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.9 [3]

A fuzzy set B in fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra nowhere dense set if there exists no non-zero fuzzy supra open set A in (M, S^*) such that $A < cl^*(B)$. That is, $int^*cl^*(B) = 0$, in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.10 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra first category set if $B = \bigvee_{i=1}^\infty (B_i)$, where (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Any other fuzzy set in (M, S^*) is said to be fuzzy supra second category space.

Definition 2.11 [2]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra boundary of B is defined as $Bd(B) = cl^*(B) \wedge cl^*(1 - B)$. Obviously $Bd(B)$ is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.12 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra simply-open set if $Bd(B)$ is a fuzzy supra no-where dense set in (M, S^*) . That is., B is an fuzzy supra simply-open set in (M, S^*) if $int^*cl^*[cl^*(B) \wedge cl^*(1 - B)] = 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.13 [2]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra semi-open set in (M, S^*) if $B \leq cl^*int^*(B)$; fuzzy supra semi-closed set in (M, S^*) if $int^*cl^*(B) \leq B$.

Definition 2.14 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set if there exists a non-zero fuzzy open set B in (M, S^*) such that $B < cl^*(B)$. That is., $int^*cl^*(B) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.15. [13]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra regular-open set if $B = int^*cl^*(B)$ and fuzzy supra regular closed set if $B = cl^*int^*(B)$ in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.1. [3]

In the fuzzy supra topological space

- (a) The closure of a fuzzy supra open set is a fuzzy supra regular closed set.
- (b) The interior of a fuzzy supra closed set is a fuzzy supra regular open set.

Theorem 2.2. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.3. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra co- σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) , then $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.4. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra dense and fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.5. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected space (M, S^*) , then $cl^*(A) \vee cl^*(1-A) = 1$ in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.6. [3]

For any fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) , the following are equivalent:

- (a) (M, S^*) is fuzzy supra basically disconnected space.
- (b) For each fuzzy supra closed G_δ -set A , $int^*(A)$ is fuzzy supra closed.
- (c) For each fuzzy supra open set F_σ -set A , $cl^*(A) + cl^*[1-cl^*(A)] = 1$.

Theorem 2.7. [3]

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra topological space. Then, the following are equivalent:

- (a) (M, S^*) is fuzzy supra hyperconnected.
- (b) Every fuzzy supra pre-open set is fuzzy supra dense set.

Theorem 2.8. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra set defined on M with $int^*(A) \neq 0$ in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected space (M, S^*) , then $int^*cl^*(A)$ and $1-int^*cl^*(A)$ are fuzzy supra resolvable sets in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.9. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra residual set in a fuzzy supra globally disconnected space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.10. [3]

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra topological space. Then, the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) (M, S^*) is fuzzy supra hyperconnected.
- (ii) 1_M and 0_M are the only fuzzy supra regular open sets in M .

Theorem 2.11. [3]

If a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra σ -Baire space, then (M, S^*)

is a fuzzy supra Volterra space.

Theorem 2.12. [3]

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra topological space. Then, the following are equivalent:

- (i) (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra weakly Baire space.
- (ii) $\text{int}^*(A) = 0$, for every fuzzy supra σ -boundary set A in (M, S^*) .
- (iii) $\text{cl}^*(B) = 1$, for every fuzzy supra co- σ -boundary set B in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.13. [3]

If a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra weakly Baire space and fuzzy supra open hereditarily irresolvable space, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space.

Theorem 2.14. [3]

If a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra weakly Baire space, then for any regular open set A in (M, S^*) , $A \wedge \text{int}^*(1-A) = 0$, in (M, S^*) .

3.Fuzzy Supra Almost P-Spaces

Definition 3.1.

A fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra almost P-space, if for every non-zero fuzzy supra G_δ -set A in (M, S^*) , $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.1.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Now $\text{int}^*(A) \leq \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A)$, implies that $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Hence, A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.2.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . By Theorem 2.1, for the fuzzy supra open set $\text{int}^*(A)$, $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.3.

If B is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 3.2, $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(1-A)$ is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) . Now $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(1-A) = 1 - \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A)$, in (M, S^*) . Then $1 - \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) and hence $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.4.

If A is a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then A is not a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) . By Theorem 2.2, A is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $\text{int}^*(1-A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 0$ and $\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 1$. Hence A is not a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.5.

If A is a fuzzy supra co- σ -boundary set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra co- σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.3, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 3.4, $\text{cl}^*(1-A) \neq 1$, in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-\text{int}^*(A) \neq 1$ and hence $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.6.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra regular closed set C in (M, S^*) such that $C \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 3.1, A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) and $\text{int}^*\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 0$. Then, there exists a non-zero fuzzy supra open set B in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$. Now $\text{cl}^*(B) \leq \text{cl}^*[\text{cl}^*(A)] = \text{cl}^*(A)$. Since B is a fuzzy supra open set, by Theorem 2.1, $\text{cl}^*(B)$ is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) . Let $C = \text{cl}^*(B)$. Thus there exists a fuzzy supra regular closed set C in (M, S^*) such that $C \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$.

Proposition 3.7.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then either A is a fuzzy supra residual set with $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$ or $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, either $\text{cl}^*(A) = 1$ or $\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 1$ in (M, S^*) . If $\text{cl}^*(A) = 1$, in (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra dense and fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . By Theorem 2.4, A is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Thus, A is a fuzzy supra residual set with $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . If $\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 1$, in (M, S^*) , then $\text{cl}^*\text{int}^*(A) \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$, implies that $\text{cl}^*\text{int}^*(A) < 1$ and then $1-\text{cl}^*\text{int}^*(A) > 0$. Thus, $\text{int}^*\text{cl}^*(1-A) > 0$. That is., $\text{int}^*\text{cl}^*(1-A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Hence, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.8.

If A is a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra first category set with $\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 1$ or A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) . By Theorem 2.2, A is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 3.7, either $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra residual set with $\text{int}^*(1-A) \neq 0$ or $1-(1-A)$ is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Thus, A is a fuzzy supra first category set with $\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 1$ or A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set

in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.9.

If A is a fuzzy supra co- σ -boundary set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then either A is a fuzzy supra residual set with $int^*(A) \neq 0$ or $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra co- σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.3, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 3.8, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra first category set with $cl^*(1-A) \neq 1$ or $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Hence A is a fuzzy supra residual set with $int^*(A) \neq 0$ or $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.10.

If A is a fuzzy supra residual set in a fuzzy supra almost P-spaces (M, S^*) , then $int^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) and then $1-A = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)$, where (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra nowhere dense sets in (M, S^*) . Let $C = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} [1-cl^*(B_i)]$. Now $1-cl^*(B_i)$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) and $C = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} [1-cl^*(B_i)]$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Also $C = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} [1-cl^*(B_i)] = 1 - [\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl^*(B_i)] \leq 1 - [\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)] = 1 - (1-A)$ and then $C \leq A$ in (M, S^*) . Then $int^*(C) \leq int^*(A)$ in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $int^*(C) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) . Hence $int^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.11.

If A is a fuzzy supra residual set in fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) then A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-spaces, by Proposition 3.10, $int^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) . Now $int^*(A) \leq int^*cl^*(A)$, implies that $int^*cl^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Hence A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.12.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then $int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $A = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_i)$, where $A_i \in S^*$. Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $int^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) and $int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Now $int^*(A) \leq A$, $int^*(A) = int^*(A) \wedge A = int^*(A) \wedge [\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_i)]$ and thus $int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) .

4. Fuzzy Supra Almost P-Spaces and Other Fuzzy Supra Topological Spaces

Proposition 4.1.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $int^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Now $int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra open set in the fuzzy supra hyperconnected space (M, S^*) and thus is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) . Then, $cl^*int^*(A) = 1$, in (M, S^*) . Now $cl^*int^*(A) \leq cl^*(A)$ implies that $1 \leq cl^*(A)$. That is., $cl^*(A) = 1$, in (M, S^*) . Hence A is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .

Remark 4.1.

In view of the above Proposition one will have the following result:” Fuzzy supra G_δ -sets in fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are fuzzy supra dense sets”.

Proposition 4.2.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (X, T) , then

- (i) $A \vee (1-A)$ is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .
- (ii) $cl^*(A) \vee cl^*(1-A) = 1$, in (M, S^*) .

Proof.(i).

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.1, A is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) . Then, $cl^*(A) = 1$, in (M, S^*) . Now $A \leq A \vee (1-A)$ implies that $cl^*(A) \leq cl^*(A \vee (1-A))$ and then $1 \leq cl^*(A \vee (1-A))$. That is., $cl^*(A \vee (1-A)) = 1$ and hence $A \vee (1-A)$ is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) .

(ii). By Proposition 3.1, the fuzzy supra G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected space, by Theorem 2.5, $cl^*(A) \vee cl^*(1-A) = 1$ in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 4.3.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra semi-open set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $int^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Now $int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected space, $int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) . Then, $cl^*int^*(A) = 1$ and thus $A \leq cl^*int^*(A)$, in (M, S^*) . Hence A is a fuzzy supra semi-open set in (M, S^*) .

The following proposition shows that fuzzy supra basically disconnected and fuzzy supra hyperconnected spaces are not fuzzy supra almost P-spaces.

Proposition 4.4.

If (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra basically disconnected and fuzzy supra hyperconnected space, then (M, S^*) is not a fuzzy supra almost P-space.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra closed G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra basically disconnected space, by Theorem 2.6, $\text{int}^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) . Then, $\text{cl}^*\text{int}^*(A) = \text{int}^*(A)$, in (M, S^*) . This implies that $\text{cl}^*\text{int}^*(A) \leq A$ and then A is a fuzzy supra pre-closed set in (M, S^*) . This implies that $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra pre-open set in (M, S^*) . Also since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected space, by Theorem 2.7, $\text{cl}^*(1-A) = 1$, in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-\text{int}^*(A) = \text{cl}^*(1-A) = 1$ and $\text{int}^*(A) = 0$, in (M, S^*) . Hence (M, S^*) is not a fuzzy supra almost P-space.

Proposition 4.5.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in the fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, then $\text{int}^*\text{cl}^*(A)$ and $1 - \text{int}^*\text{cl}^*(A)$ are fuzzy supra resolvable sets in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) . Also since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected space, by Theorem 2.8, $\text{int}^*\text{cl}^*(A)$ and $1-\text{int}^*\text{cl}^*(A)$ are fuzzy supra resolvable sets in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 4.6.

If A is a fuzzy supra residual set in a fuzzy supra globally disconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra globally disconnected space, by Theorem 2.9, A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Now $\text{int}^*(A) \leq \text{int}^*\text{cl}^*(A)$, implies that $\text{int}^*\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 0$ and hence A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 4.7.

If A is a fuzzy supra residual set in a fuzzy supra globally disconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra regular closed set C in (M, S^*) such that $C \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra globally disconnected space, by Theorem 2.9, A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 3.6, there exists a fuzzy supra regular closed set C in (M, S^*) such that $C \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$.

A condition for fuzzy supra door spaces to become fuzzy supra almost P-spaces, is obtained by means of somewhere denseness of fuzzy supra closed sets.

Proposition 4.8.

If fuzzy supra closed sets are fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets in a fuzzy supra door space (M, S^*) , then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space.

Proof.

Let (A_i) 's ($i=1$ to ∞) be fuzzy supra sets defined on M in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra door space, (A_i) 's are either fuzzy supra open or fuzzy supra closed in (M, S^*) . Now consider those fuzzy supra sets (A_i) 's which are fuzzy supra open in (M, S^*) .

Let $B = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_i)$ where (A_i) 's are the fuzzy supra open sets from (A_i) 's in (M, S^*) . Then, B is a fuzzy supra G_{δ} -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra door space, the fuzzy supra set B is either fuzzy supra open or fuzzy supra closed in (M, S^*) . If B is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) , then $int^*(B) = B \neq 0$. If B is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) , then $cl^*(B) = B$ and $int^*cl^*(B) = int^*(B)$. By hypothesis, fuzzy supra closed sets are fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets in (M, S^*) and then $int^*cl^*(B) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . This implies that $int^*(B) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Hence in both cases, $int^*(B) \neq 0$, for the fuzzy supra G_{δ} -set B in (M, S^*) . Hence (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space.

Proposition 4.9.

If $B (\neq 1)$ is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then B is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let $B (\neq 1)$ is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 3.3, $int^*cl^*(B)$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) . Also since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected space, by Theorem 2.10, 1_X and 0_X are the only fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M, S^*) . Then, $int^*cl^*(B) = 0$ or $int^*cl^*(B) = 1$, in (M, S^*) . Now $int^*cl^*(B) = 1$ implies that $cl^*(B) = 0$ and then B is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) such that $cl^*(B) = 1$. But this is a contradiction to (M, S^*) being a fuzzy supra almost P-space. Thus, $int^*cl^*(B) \neq 1$, in (M, S^*) . Then, $int^*cl^*(B) = 0$ and $int^*(B) \leq int^*cl^*(B)$, implies that $int^*(B) = 0$, in (M, S^*) . Thus, B is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) such that $int^*(B) = 0$ in (M, S^*) and hence B is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

The following proposition shows that fuzzy supra F_{σ} -sets in fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are fuzzy supra first category sets.

Proposition 4.10.

If $A (\neq 1)$ is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let $A (\neq 1)$ be a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.9, A is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) and thus A is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) with $int^*(A) = 0$. Then, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra G_{δ} -set with $cl^*(1-A) = 1 - int^*(A) = 1 - 0 = 1$, in (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.4, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra residual set in (M, S^*) . Hence A is a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) .

The following proposition gives a condition under which fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space become fuzzy supra σ -Baire spaces.

Proposition 4.11.

If $int^*[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)] = 0$, where (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra F_{σ} -sets in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra σ -Baire space.

Proof.

Let (A_i) 's be fuzzy supra F_{σ} -sets in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.9, (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense sets in (M, S^*) . By hypothesis, $int^*[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_i)] = 0$, where (A_i) 's are fuzzy

supra σ -nowhere dense sets in (M, S^*) . Hence (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra σ -Baire space.

Proposition 4.12.

If $\text{int}^*[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(B_i)]=0$, where (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra F_{σ} -sets in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Voltra space.

Proof.

The proof follows from Proposition 4.11 and Theorem 2.11.

The following proposition gives a condition under which fuzzy supra almost P-spaces become fuzzy supra P-spaces.

Proposition 4.13.

If (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra globally disconnected, fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra P-space.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_{δ} -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.3, A is a fuzzy supra semi-open set in (M, S^*) . Also since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra globally disconnected space, the fuzzy supra semi-open set A is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Hence (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra P-space.

Proposition 4.14.

If $A(\neq 1)$ is a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then

- (i) A is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) .
- (ii) A is a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

(i) Let A be a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.2, A is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.9, A is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

(ii). By Theorem 2.2, the fuzzy supra σ -boundary set A is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) . Then, by Proposition 4.10, A is a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) .

The following proposition shows that fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are fuzzy supra weakly Baire spaces.

Proposition 4.15.

If (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra weakly Baire space.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra σ -boundary set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.14 (i), A is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Then, A is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) with $\text{int}^*(A)=0$. Thus, for the fuzzy supra σ -boundary set A in (M, S^*) , $\text{int}^*(A)=0$, implies, by Theorem 2.12, that (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra weakly Baire space.

Proposition 4.16.

If (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra open hereditarily irresolvable, fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space.

Proof.

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.15, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra weakly Baire space. Thus (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra open hereditarily irresolvable and fuzzy supra weakly Baire space. Then, by Theorem 2.13, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra Baire space.

Proposition 4.17.

If (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, then A and $1-cl^*(A)$ are disjoint fuzzy supra sets for any fuzzy supra regular open set A in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.15, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra weakly Baire space. Then, by Theorem 2.14, for the fuzzy supra regular open set A , $A \wedge int^*(1-A) = 0$, in (M, S^*) and then $A \wedge (1-cl^*(A)) = 0$, in (M, S^*) . Hence A and $1-cl^*(A)$ are disjoint fuzzy supra sets in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 4.18.

If A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra F_σ -set B in (M, S^*) such that $cl^*(A \vee B) = 1$, in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.2(i), $A \vee (1-A)$ is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) . Since A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) , $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Let $B = 1-A$ and then B is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $A \vee B$ is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) and hence $cl^*(A \vee B) = 1$, in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 4.19.

If (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra irresolvable space.

Proof.

Let $A (\neq 0)$ be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, by Proposition 4.2(i), $A \vee (1-A)$ is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) . Let $C = A \vee (1-A)$. Then, $cl^*(C) = 1$, in (M, S^*) . Since A is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) , $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Let $B = 1-A$ and $A \neq 0$, implies that $B \neq 1$. Thus $B (\neq 1)$ is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, by Proposition 4.9, B is a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) and thus B is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) with $int^*(B) = 0$, in (M, S^*) . Now $cl^*(1-C) = cl^*(1-[A \vee (1-A)]) = cl^*(1-[A \vee B]) = 1 - int^*[A \vee B] \leq 1 - (int^*[A] \vee int^*[B]) = 1 - (int^*[A] \vee 0) = 1 - int^*[A]$. Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space, $int^*(A) \neq 0$ and thus $1 - int^*[A]$ is a non-zero fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) . Thus, $cl^*(1-C) \leq 1 - int^*[A]$ implies that $cl^*(1-C) \neq 1$. Hence, for a fuzzy supra dense set C in (M, S^*) , $cl^*(1-C) \neq 1$, implies that (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra irresolvable space.

Proposition 4.20.

If $A(\neq 1)$ is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra F_σ -set B in (M, S^*) such that $A \leq B$.

Proof.

Let $A(\neq 1)$ be a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space, By Proposition 4.10, A is a fuzzy supra first category set in (M, S^*) . Then, $A = (\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty C_i)$, where (C_i) 's are fuzzy supra nowhere dense sets in (M, S^*) . Let $\theta = \bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty [1-cl^*(C_i)]$. Now $1-cl^*(C_i)$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) and $\theta = \bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty (1-cl^*(C_i))$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Also $\theta = \bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty [1-cl^*(C_i)] = 1 - [\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty cl^*(C_i)] \leq 1 - [\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty (C_i)] = 1 - A$ and then $A \leq 1 - \theta$ in (M, S^*) . Let $B = 1 - \theta$ and thus B is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set, in (M, S^*) . Hence, for the fuzzy supra F_σ -set A , there exists a fuzzy supra F_σ -set B in (M, S^*) such that $A \leq B$.

Proposition 4.21.

If $A(\neq 0)$ is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra G_δ -set B in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq A$.

Proof.

Let $A(\neq 0)$ be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1 - A$ is a fuzzy supra F_σ -set in the fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space (M, S^*) . Then, by Proposition 4.20, there exists a fuzzy supra F_σ -set C in (M, S^*) such that $1 - A \leq C$ and $1 - C \leq A$. Let $B = 1 - C$. Then, B is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Hence, for the fuzzy supra G_δ -set A , there exists a fuzzy supra G_δ -set B in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq A$.

Proposition 4.22.

If a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra P-space, then (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra basically disconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra P-space, A is a fuzzy supra open set and hence $int^*(A) = A \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . This implies that (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra almost P-space. By Proposition 4.1, (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra basically disconnected space. Hence (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra basically disconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-space.

5. Conclusion

In this paper it is established that fuzzy supra G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra residual sets in fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets. It is obtained that fuzzy supra σ -boundary sets in fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are either fuzzy supra first category sets which are not dense or fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets. It is established that fuzzy supra G_δ -sets in fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are fuzzy supra dense sets. It is obtained that fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are fuzzy supra semi-P-spaces and fuzzy supra weakly Baire spaces. It is established that fuzzy supra basically disconnected and fuzzy supra hyperconnected spaces are not fuzzy supra almost P-spaces. A condition is obtained for fuzzy supra door spaces to become fuzzy supra almost P-spaces by means of somewhere denseness of fuzzy supra closed sets. It is established that fuzzy supra globally disconnected, fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are fuzzy supra P-spaces. The conditions under which fuzzy supra almost P-spaces become fuzzy supra Baire spaces, are also obtained. It is obtained that fuzzy supra hyperconnected and fuzzy supra almost P-spaces are fuzzy supra irresolvable spaces.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this article.

References

- [1]. Abd El-Monsef, M. E. and Ramadan, A. E.,(1987), On fuzzy supra topological spaces, Indian J. Pure Appl.Math., Vol.18(4), 322-329.
- [2]. Ahmed S, Chandra Chetia B (2014), On Certain properties of fuzzy supra semi open sets, International Journal of Fuzzy Mathematics and Systems, Vol.4(1), 93-98.
- [3]. Celine A (2023), A Study on Fuzzy Supra Baire Spaces, Ph.D Thesis, Thiruvalluvar University, Tamilnadu, India.
- [4]. Chang. C.L. (1968), Fuzzy topological spaces, Journal of Mathematical Analysis and applications, Vol.24, 182-190.
- [5]. Cohen.L.W and Goffman.C (1949), A theory of transfinite convergence, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc., Vol.66, 65-74.
- [6]. C.I Kim, Almost P-spaces, Commun. Korean Math. Soc., 18(4),(2003), 695-701.
- [7]. R.Levy, Almost P-spaces, Canad. J. Math. XXIX(5) (1977), 284 - 288.
- [8]. Mashhour A.S., Allam A.A., Mahmoud F.S and Khedr F.H., (1983), On Supra Topological Spaces, Indian J. Pure and Appl. Math., Vol.4(14), 502-510.
- [9]. Mishra.A.K.,(1972), Topological view of P-spaces, Gen. Topology Appl. Vol.2(4), 349-362.
- [10] Sahidul Ahmed and Biman Chandra Chetia (2014), On Certain Properties of Fuzzy Supra Semi open Sets, International Journal of Fuzzy Mathematics and Systems, Vol.4(1), 93-98.
- [11] Selvakumar K, Mahaboob Hassain Sherieff K and Vinothkumar A (2023), On Fuzzy Supra P-space, Stochastic Modelling and Computational Sciences Vol.3(1), 237-243.
- [12] Selvakumar K, Mahaboob Hassain Sherieff K and Vinothkumar A (2025), On Weak Fuzzy Supra P-space, High Technology Letters, Vol.31(7), 1-10.
- [13] Sikorski.R (1950), Remarks on spaces of high power, Fund. Math. Vol.37, 125-136.
- [14] Srikiruthika J, Kalaichelvi A., Fuzzy Supra Regular Open Sets, International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Vol.119(15) (2018), 731-735.
- [15] Thangaraj.G and Balasubramanian.G (2001), On Fuzzy Basically Disconnected Spaces, J.Fuzzy Math. Vol.9(1), 103-110.
- [16]. A.I.Veksler, P'-points, P'-sets, P'-spaces a new class of order - continuous measure and functionals, Soviet Math. Dokl. No. 4 (5) (1973) 1445 - 1450.
- [17]. Zadeh. L.A (1965), Fuzzy sets, Informatics and Control, Vol.8, 338-353.